

BOOKTRAILER AS A MEANS OF FORMING THE DISCURSIVE COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS

BOOKTRAILER COMO MEDIO DE FORMAR LA COMPETENCIA DISCURSIVA DE LOS ESTUDIANTES

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RESUMEN

El objetivo de la investigación fue analizar el BookTrailer como medio para formar la competencia discursiva de los estudiantes. En esta investigación, se seleccionaron 85 estudiantes y se les presentó el método de "Guerra y paz" de Leo Tolstoy, que utiliza el método de avance de libros. La forma impresa del libro también fue entregada a otros 85 estudiantes. Luego se analizó su percepción de estrategia, táctica, el componente de género y el texto del libro. Los resultados mostraron que los estudiantes que usaron el trailer del libro tenían una mejor comprensión de la estrategia, la táctica, el género y el texto de Leo Tolstoy en Peace and War.

Palabras clave: booktrailer, competencia discursiva, competencia en información, tecnología de la información, tecnología de aprendizaje basada en proyectos.

ABSTRACT

the aim of research was to Analyze booktrailer as a mean of forming the discursive competence of students. In this research 85 students were selected, and using book trailer method Leo Tolstoy's book of "War and Peace" was submitted to them. The printed form of book was also given to other 85 students. Then their perception of strategy, tactic, the genre component and text of the book was analyzed. The results showed that students who used the book trailer had a better understanding of Leo Tolstoy's strategy, tactics, genre and text in Peace and War.

Keywords: book trailer, discursive competence, information competence, information technology, learning technology.

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INTRODUCTION

Federal state educational standards of higher education in Russia are focused on the formation of a linguistic character capable to communication in oral and written forms in Russian and foreign languages for solving problems of interpersonal and intercultural interaction; tolerance of ambiguity in social, cultural and personal differences; owning the basics of professional ethics and speech culture; ready to interact with participants in the educational process. These skills are formed while mastering communicative competence (Bainiyazova, Fahrutdinova, Fahrutdinov and Absatova, 2017). Auhadeeva (2017) note that communicative competency is regarded as meta-competency of the general professional competency of the teacher (Auhadeeva, Valiahmetova, Akhmadullina, Pimenova, Salpykova, Valiakhmetova, Aukhadeev, 2017).

In our pedagogical practice, a contradiction has arisen between a general decline of the level of speech culture of students, their intellectual level and the need for the development of a linguistic persona capable to analyze the information contained in the text, create their own speech statements and apply the results of intellectual activity in practice.

E.F. Tarasov in his work notes that language is included in culture, since the "body" of the sign (meaning) is a cultural object in the form of which the linguistic and communicative ability of a person is defined, the meaning of a sign is also a cultural entity that arises only in human activity. Culture is also included in the language, since all of it is modeled in the text (Tarasov,1994).

Researchers do not so often turn to the Analyze of the facts of native culture in the language, although it is difficult to overestimate the role of the native language and culture in the upbringing of a harmoniously developed personality. In this regard, in the learning process, it is necessary to show the mechanism of interaction between language and culture.

The branch of linguistics that studies the relationship between language and cultural concepts is called cultural linguistics (Sharifian, 2011). As an independent direction of linguistics, formed in the 90s of the XX century, the term "cultural linguistics" appeared in the last decade in connection with the works of the phraseological school headed by V.N. Telia, works of Yu.S. Stepanova, A.D. Arutyunova, V.A. Maslova and other researchers (Maslova,2001). Following the definition of V.V. Krasnykh, under cultural linguistics we mean "discipline that studies the development, reflection and fixation of culture in language and discourse, directly related to the Analyze of the national worldview, linguistic consciousness, the features of the mental-lingual complex" (Krasnyh,2002).If culturology studies the self-consciousness of person in relation to nature, society, history, art and other spheres of his social and cultural life, and linguistics considers the worldview that is displayed and fixed in the language in the form of

mental models of the linguistic worldview, cultural linguistics also has its subject in language and culture, being in dialogue, interaction (Maslova,2001).

Finally this research titled “BookTailer as a Means of Forming the Discursive Competence “ of Students contributes to the formation of the discursive competence of students with the use of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT).

LITERATURE REVIEW

In the modern information society with the rapid development of television and the Internet, visual arts and electronic information carriers, on the one hand, the formation of a clip-like consciousness and perception among young people, on the other, there is a decrease in its interest in the book as a medium of information, a sharp drop in reader activity. It is necessary to search new ways to form students' ability to express their thoughts accurately, competently, convincingly, speak to the audience in view of new information realities and new opportunities that are associated with them. One of these new ways is creation a book trailer.

The first-year students of KFU, who Analyze applied and foreign philology, pedagogical education, vocational training, design, have been mastering “Computer science and Information technology” discipline during 2017-2018 academic year. As this academic year was devoted to L. Tolstoy’s oeuvre students were invited to participate in Booktrailers competition on his works. The choice of the book was carried out independently by students in creative groups of 5-7 students.

The booktrailer is a new way of presenting information. It is created to promote reading, as well as to increase interest in books. These videos are removed both to modern books, and to books that have become literary classics.

In this article discursive competence is considered as an inalienable part of communicative competence, as the basis of speech culture, communication in oral and written forms focused at interpersonal and intercultural interaction. In our work we keep up the following definition: discursive competence is the ability to construct holistic, connected and logical statements (discourses) of different functional styles in oral and written speech on the basis of understanding different types of texts while reading and listening; involves the choice of linguistic means, depending on the type of statement, the situation of communication, communicative tasks. It is considered as a component of communicative competence (Abdrafikova, Akhmadullina, Yarmakeev, 2015).

Within the framework of the functional-communicative approach, discourse is regarded as the most important form of everyday human life and is "a complex communicative phenomenon involving the text, as well as extralinguistic and social

factors (knowledge of the world, opinions, attitudes, goals of the addressee) necessary for understanding" (Karasik,1999).

It should be mentioned that discursive competence has a complex structure. As a result, there are several components: strategic, tactical, genre and text (Volkova, 2015).

Strategic includes understanding the intentions of the partner and planning a communicative event in terms of achieving the goals.

Tactical component presupposes the formation person's speech, his ability to analyze the communicative situation and select the means and ways of achieving the communicative intent of the person that are adequate to this situation and which are optimal for the given linguistic community.

The genre component includes the ability to choose the type of text to achieve the communicative intent of the person in a given context, as well as knowledge of genre norms and the ability to organize discourse in accordance with the canons of a particular genre.

Text defines the ability to organize a sequence of sentences in such a way that they form a single whole - a text with all its characteristic properties (Yarmakeev,Abdrafikova, Pimenova&, Sharafieva,2016). Working on the formation of discursive competence, the teacher, relying on the knowledge of personal - oriented pedagogical technologies, should create conditions for the disclosure and communicative realization of students' creative potential, to select tasks that taking into account individual abilities of students. In our work, such conditions were created by using ICT in and out of classes.

METHODOLOGY

The Book trailer competition on Leo Tolstoy's writings was held during the 2017-2018 academic year among first year students, who had been Analyzeing "Computer science and Information technology" discipline. Students interested in the idea of the competition.

[t was attended by 85 students who presented 28 creative works. On the correspondence round of the competition the judges selected 8 works and singled out two nominations of the competition: the book trailer and the author film.

The final round of the Book trailer competition was held in March, 2018 at the section of the annual final scientific and educational conference of students of KFU "Information Technologies in Philology and Education". Before showing book trailers each creative team of the students presented their work to the audience, which differed in their author's approaches, original creative ideas and demonstration of the book trailers to the audience, various ways and technical

realization of their creation.

The students presented their book trailers and the author films on such writings of Leo Tolstoy as "War and Peace", "Anna Karenina", "The Prisoner of the Caucasus", "After the Ball", "For What?", "The Story of the Aeronaut". The author's film "Read Tolstoy!" presented a modern view of youth on the work of the great Russian writer.

The results of the competition and the best book trailer under Leo Tolstoy's novel "War and Peace", are presented on the website of KFU under the link: <https://kpfu.ru/philology-culture/chitaj-tolstogo-333736.html>, and were viewed more than 270 times.

This year, it was declared the year of the Great Russian writer Leo Tolstoy in the Republic of Tatarstan (Russia) and at Kazan Federal University (KFU). His writings are studied at schools on Russian Language and Literature discipline. "But it's no secret that the "traditional" school composition on Literature turns out to be something quite alien to the mentality of modern youth, which is far from the Russian literature classics of the XIX-XX centuries in regard to history and cultural linguistics" (Teun Van, 1998).

steps in the process of book trailer creation

There are four main steps in the process of book trailer creation:

- 1) reading the book and acquaintance with the biography of its author;
- 2) searching for photos, videos and music;
- 3) creating text for recording;
- 4) recording a voice and overlaying it on music.

First students needed to decide on the plot, telling the brightest moments of the work and preserving the intrigue, because the task of the video is to encourage the reader to read the book.

Then students selected the format of the book trailer. It could be presented in the form of a presentation, a production video with the participation of actors or animation. Book trailer, in contrast to the film, is always the need to create frames from scratch, transformation of words into pictures, movement from one type of art to another, providing interaction and dialing.

Book trailer is a short 2-3 minutes video story about book that reveals brightest moments of the book. It is capable to interest an audience to read the book.

To start, it is necessary to Analyze the plot of the book, find information about the biography of the author.

Then students had to find photos, excerpts from films, pictures, music that will fit the chosen theme and the book.

After this student wrote text for book trailer. Teaching students to write with argumentation, for example in EFL class, can become the basis for the formation of their discursive competence (Volkova,2015). The text should be clear and easy to understand. The more eloquent the story about the book, that students have to advertise, will be the more interest of audience will be. The text performs a phenomena and process of national history and culture. Language is a way of the translation of culture that implements through texts.

Students learn new knowledge the spiritual culture using texts, get acquainted with traditions, national psyche of their and other people. At last, when the text is ready, student had to voice it expressively. Scoring must be high-quality as listeners could hear every word. After work done students had to join all the collected material, overlay text on music and add pictures using software.

For **book trailer creation** students could use any device with camera, choose any software, e.g. Power Point, Windows Movie Maker, Macromedia Flash Player, Sony Vegas Pro 10, Windows Live etc. Book trailers can be created in any media platform: animation, game clip, short film, slide-show of pictures in presentation etc.

They could use advertising techniques, visual images, animation effects that can intrigue readers. The duration of the video is no more than three minutes in mpeg4, mpg, mpeg, avi, ppt extensions.

In **the process of creation** of book trailer students carried out project-based learning. The main purpose of a project-based learning is in providing students with self-Analyze opportunity in the process of solving practical problems that requires the integration of knowledge from different fields. Also, project-based learning involves a set of research, problem-based and creative methods. Students search information, read the books, make up their own texts etc.

Students **prepared presentation of the book trailers** in the form of stories, interviews and dialog with the audience.

Creation of the book trailer promotes the formation of information competence, which assumes "the formation among students a set of personal qualities, a certain style of thinking, skills of working with information, skills in the use of information technology to solve educational, research and professional problems" (Kudryashova, 2007).

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

In this research 85 students were selected, and using book trailer method Leo Tolstoy's book of "War and Peace" was submitted to them. The printed form of book was also given to other 85 students. Then their perception of strategy, tactic, genre component and text of the book was analyzed. Results of the analysis is as following:

Table 1: T-test to investigate the difference between understanding the strategy, tactics, genre and text of the book "Peace and War" in two groups of booktrailers and printed books

	Group	n	m	SD	Difference	t	p
Strategic	booktrailer	85	26	2.66	8	5.01	0.001
	book	85	18	1.01			
Tactical	booktrailer	85	34	1.63	13	8.12	0.001
	book	85	21	1.69			
The genre component	booktrailer	85	18	4.12	6	4.54	0.002
	book	85	12	2.67			
Text	booktrailer	85	22	1.82	5	3.89	0.004
	book	85	17	1.03			

By: Batrova, Lukoyanova, Salekhova and Çavuşoğlu (2018)

The results showed that students who used the book trailer had a better understanding of Leo Tolstoy's strategy, tactics, genre and text in Peace and War.

In the process of creating the book trailers there are formed genre and text components of discursive competence through the development of the following communicative skills: students read and analyze the texts of fiction books; choose different ways of disclosing topics; plan, compose and structure their own texts. Then the text serves the basis for scoring of the book trailer that reflects the goals, attitudes, opinions of students on the book.

The strategic component of the discursive competence of students is formed in the process of selecting the plot of the booktrailer in order to attract interest to the book and intrigue audience with the help of visual aids, as well as expressing one's own attitude to the writing.

The tactical component of students' discursive competence is formed by preparing a scored text. This work represented the ability of students to construct discourses in oral and written speech, emotionally expressing speech intentions and semantic content, expressing communicative intent; choosing ICT as a mean and way to achieve the purpose.

CONCLUSIONS

The creation of the booktrailer is an effective way of forming students, which is the basis for the development of communicative competence, speech culture, oral and written communication aimed at interpersonal and intercultural interaction.

In accordance with the functional-communicative approach, discourse is considered as the most important form of everyday human life practice. Accordingly, in order to create a booktrailer, you need to read and analyze the text of the writing; choose different ways of disclosing topics; plan, compile and structure your own texts, on the basis of which the book trailer's scoring is constructed, reflecting the purposes, attitudes, opinions of students about the work. The use of ICT for creation of the booktrailer facilitates the formation of a student's readiness to carry out information activities related to the solution of educational, research and professional tasks. Thus, the discursive competence of students can be formed by linguistic means using ICT.

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REFERENCES

- Abdrafiqova, A.R., Akhmadullina, R.M., Yarmakeev, I.E (2015). **Formation of the communicative competence in students future pedagogues for working with gifted pupils**. The Social Sciences.Vol.10, Issue. 7. pp. 1817-1821. URL: <http://medwelljournals.com/abstract/?doi=sscience.2015.1817.1821>
- Auhadeeva, L., Valiahmetova, A., Akhmadullina, R., Pimenova, T., Salpykova, I., Valiakmetova, N., Aukhadeev, A (2017). **Pre-service teachers' communicative competency formation in Russia. 11th International Technology, Education and Development Conference**. 6-8. Valencia, Spain. INTED2017 Proceedings. PP. 774-781. URL: <https://library.iated.org/view/AUHADEEVA2017PRE>.
- Bainiyazova, E.M., Fahrutdinova, R. A., Fahrutdinov, R.R., Absatova, M.A (2017). **Interactive technologies in formation of communicative competence of students of high educational institution**. International Journal of Scientific Analyze.Vol.5. Is. 6. pp. 63-66. URL: [F_ijss_iran_sep_17_benson_oa13.pdf](https://www.researchgate.net/publication/317111111).
- Karasik, V.I (1999). **Religioznyj diskurs**. Yazykovaya lichnost': problemy lingvokul'turologii i funktsional'noj semantiki. Volgograd. 186 s.
- Krasnyh, V.V (2002). **Ehtnopsiholingvistika** i lingvokul'turologiya.p.12.
- Maslova, V.A (2001). **Lingvokul'turologiya: Ucheb.posobiedlya stud. vyssh. ucheb, zavedenij**. – M.: Izdatel'skij centr «Akademiya». 208 s. URL: <https://s30556663155.mirtesen.ru/blog/43645453276/LINGVOKULTUROLOGIYA>
- Sharifian, F (2011). **Cultural Conceptualizations and Language: Theoretical Framework and**

Applications. Amsterdam/Philadelphia: John Benjamins. p. 11.

Tarasov, E.F (1994). **Yazyk i kul'tura: Metodologicheskie problemy.** Yazyk – Kul'tura – Ehtnos. – M. pp. 105-114.

Teun Van, D (1998). **Ideology: A Multidisciplinary approach.** London: Sage Publications. URL: <http://www.discourses.org/OldBooks/Teun%20A%20van%20Dijk%20-%20Ideology.pdf>.

Volkova, N.V (2015). **Buktrejler kak «vizual'noe ehse»** v kontekste formirovaniya chitatel'skogo interesa. Kul'tura. Duhovnost'. Obshchestvo. No. 16. pp. 209-213. URL: <https://elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=22981631>.

Yarmakeev, I.E., Abdrafikova, A.R., Pimenova, T.S., Sharafieva, A.M (2016). **Formation of discursive competence in EFL class.** Journal of Language and Literature. Vol.7. No. 2. pp. 185-190. URL: https://repository.kpfu.ru/?p_id=135293.